

Intellectuals and The Human Vices

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Human vices and virtues have often tried to overweigh each other and humanity has always wished the later to be on the heavier side. Vices, bad as such, become worse when they are associated with intellect. An intellectual's vice can do larger damage to the society, than a commoner's could do. That is why, mankind has to safeguard its intellectuals from all the vices, but who would take the responsibility? It's the intellectuals who should safeguard the mankind.

*"That if gold rust, what shall iron do?"
For if a priest be foul (in whom we trust)
No wonder is a lewd man to rust
And shame it is, if that a priest take keep,
A shit n shepherd and a clean sheep.*

(Line 500-504, General Prologue to THE CANTERBURY TALES, Geoffrey Chaucer, Put into modern spelling by Michael Murphy.)

I feel that the strongest challenges that the intellectuals face today are not as much from the outer world as are from their own mental faculty. The intellectuals are challenged by their own vices - pretensions, dogmatism, complexes, self-centeredness and greed for recognition are only a few to mention. I wish to take up a few of the intellectual vices here in this article and discuss how they act as a challenge before the intellectual pursuit.

Mass media, Mass production, Mass movement and Mass culture has made us think in such a way that we consider anything worthwhile only if it has appeal. Moreover, a product of intellect, today, is valued at its instant pragmatic value. The intellectuals being a part of this Mass culture subjugate their best faculty to the popular applause.

The applied science therefore gains importance over the pure sciences; popular literature gains importance over pure literature and commercial art over pure art. Intellectuals today, find it difficult to resist the forces of mass culture on the one hand and the temptation of instant fame, on the other. They look up to the masses for approval, they begin to think and work not towards perfection but towards popularity. Mass culture and the nuances have brought along with them a challenge for the thinking minds. If Copernicus and Archimedes would have subdued their mental faculties to the mass approval, the world today might have been living by the Ptolemy's theory. The Sun still would be believed to be moving round the Earth. For the growth of human knowledge, true intellectual pursuits have to overcome the challenge of mass approval.

The rapidity with which the global scenario is changing today has also become a challenge before the intellectuals. Whenever an intellectual begins to work upon a new hypothesis, he is threatened by the fast rate of change that is taking place around him. He is aware of the fact that by the time he completes his work and arrives at the conclusion, the hypothesis would have already been proved outdated or at least would have lost its pragmatic value. If we take example from the field of literature, few people would sit to write a great piece of literature, i.e. an epic, today. This is mainly because, by the time the epic will be completed, the reading public would have changed its taste. So the intellectual today has the challenge of speed as he has to keep pace with the fast changing world. Quality is, therefore, overshadowed by the speed. The basic concept of, 'the truth, the beauty and the good' which used to guide the intellectuals of the

past seem to be lost in the antiquity. Today, an intellectual subjugates his creative pursuits to the wish of the masses. A direct consequence of this phenomenon is to be seen in the form of a lot of popularity awards that have come up these days. More awards are given for the 'most popular' and not for 'the best'. Popularity, recognition and instant fame are temptations, difficult to overcome. Thus, modern mindedness comes as an obstacle before the intellectuals. An intellectual, today wants to be ahead of others, in the time parameters and not in the parameters of quality. He wants to think what others are yet to think; he wants to create what others are yet to create and he wants to say what others are yet to say (and in all likelihood, in the latest jargon). If an intellectual is inspired by the concept of perfection, he has to overcome the challenge of speed. If an intellectual has to work towards the betterment of the human civilisation, he has to expand the horizons of his vision beyond the present and the immediate. It is well expected of a commoner to think in terms of immediate results. A layman justly expects a clear balance-sheet of his efforts and results but an intellectual has to think in abstract terms. Surprisingly, the present day intellectual is facing a stronger challenge in this regard. And why not? Doesn't one need greater degree of self discipline and self restraint to resist the temptation that the various popularity awards bring along with them? These popularity awards and the repeated recognitions in the print and visual media carry away many gems of the intellectuals to the winds.

Another of the grave intellectual challenges appears in the form of intellectual impartiality. An intellectual has to have, or at least, develop a kind of 'emotional generality' and 'logical impartiality' (phrases used by Bertrand Russell in the essay "Philosophy for layman" in his book "UNPOPULAR ESSAYS"). That is an intellectual is expected to evaluate a given concept objectively without any emotional bias, fear or any interplay of self esteem. He should think in an objective manner and never value the source and the origin of a concept but the concept should be valued on its own merits. Let me take an example to explain this. Suppose I bring out a theory of my own and discuss it with some of my students. There are six out of ten chances that I don't

expect my students to disqualify or contradict my theory. Because my self esteem comes in the way. If a student however comes out with an equally comprehensive but opposing point of view, I do not welcome it with complete emotional impartiality because my own ideology entraps my logical faculty. A true intellectual overcomes this obstacle of self esteem. But in some cases, self esteem entraps an intellectual's mental faculty to such a degree that he closes all the corridors of objective thinking. Such intellectuals often become completely wrapped into their own ideologies. Such people are self convinced of their supremacy and often tend to reject all new ideas without even probing into the details. One would often see such intellectuals behaving in a whimsical manner. One of the strong challenges before an intellectual is to overcome his own whims and to develop logical and emotional generality along with objective thinking. The inherent quality of objective thinking and emotional generality is one of the greatest intellectual virtues. To take an example of emotional generality, I prefer quoting the life of Mother Teresa. She could feel the sufferings and pains of one and the all with the same emotional intensity as one would feel for his kins. Almost every philosophy of the world advocates emotional generality as could be seen in proverbs such as "love thy neighbours as thy self", "*vasudhaiv kutumbhkam*".

No intellectual growth can take place but for independent thinking. Columbus could think independently and could work on his conviction. Milton could resist the forces of his times and Wordsworth could dare to walk on solitary path. Had the intellectuals not dared to think independently, the world of human awareness would have stagnated. 'Independent thinking' of the earlier times is however becoming obsolete these days. The intellectuals today try to think what is being thought globally and what could be approved globally. Thus, the huge number of researchers in various fields have not been able to produce a proportionate amount of novel ideas and concepts.

The intellectual today has to overcome his own vices and develop a habit of independent thinking, besides fighting the outer pressures of the societies. The habit of independent thinking would also bring about a reduction in pseudo-intellectualism.